

MORALITY DILEMMAS IN THE NOVELS OF IAN MCEWAN COGNITIVE APPROACHES TO "THE CHILDREN ACT" BY IAN MCEWAN

Chulyukina Anna Alekseyevna

Master's student at UZSWLU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19084399>

Abstract

The article is devoted how readers perceive the information in one of Ian McEwan's novel The Children Act with a help of cognitive approaches. Each cognitive concept is supported by extract from the book. Having unique view of the world all readers create a certain image of the situation with common features that are build by means of cognitive concepts.

Keywords: cognitive poetics, figure and ground, deixis, background, prototype.

The novel The Children Act by Ian McEwan is a work that describes moral choices, professional responsibility and psychological price of judicial power. The main character of the novel is Fiona Maye who is a high court judge, who mostly deals with family issues. The novel makes reader feel ethical dilemma and doesn't leave after reading. The decisions made by Fiona considering a young man Adam Henry, who is 17 Jehovah's Witness refusing to have blood transfusion due to his belief, relives emotional, cognitive, narrative complexity of boundaries in faith and adulthood. The case make Fiona come across not only with bad medical condition of the teenage boy but with psychological tension, that later leads to tragic situation.

Cognitive poetics described by Stockwell offers productive theoretical analysis, it focuses on how readers create meaning through conceptual structures, perceptual signs and experience. Such concepts as figure and ground, deixis, scripts schema and text worlds let us readers shape the same emotional attitude with Fiona. Stockwell says, that reading is a process of negotiation between text signs and cognitive expectations, when "perception and imagination blend into coherent mental world" (Stockwell, p. 27). The novel The Children act shows the dynamic development from Fiona's thoughts of legal reasoning, her emotional breaks, idolization of Adam and this all leads a reader to hesitate between professional impartiality and human vulnerability.

Being the central principal in Cognitive Poetics by Stockwell, the figure-ground helps explain how readers differentiate main elements in narration. According Stockwell, figure is something that is main, that is moved forward with a help of textual details, emotional charge, movement or unusual framing, while ground is a background against which meaning emerges (Stockwell, Cognitive Poetics, p. 15-18). The author of the novel puts Fiona as a dominant figure, readers follow her inner discussions, her emotional reactions, her actions, while the other characters, including Adam, serve as figure or ground depending on the emotional state of the main character, moral or psychological obligation of narration.

From the first chapters we face the professional world of Fiona, it is foregrounded with precise and accurate details of her occupation, "stacks and files" and statutory language that forms her daily environment. These documents about law form a background of her cognitive world, which is stable, structured and impersonal. Her personal crisis is when her husband reveals to have a little romance turns into sharp and harsh element of background that tremendously changes ordinary life of Fiona. The contrast between the solidity of law and the

fluidity of private emotions creates a cognitive tension that echoes the figure ground tandem described by Stockwell (p. 20).

Adam Henry initially belongs to Court ground of Fiona, he is one of participants of her case, complicated and trapped in ethical norms. Everything changes when Fiona meets Adam in the hospital, the author of the novel turns Adam from ground into figure. The perceptual focus on his appearance "thin as blade", yet unexpectedly animated, playing the violin for her (pp 118 – 121) – draws readers attention to his vitality, his youth, and his poetic imagination. The hospital room becomes a new background, where Fiona and Adam are main figures, creating strong cognitive alignment. That what was said by Stockwell, attention is grabbed by movement, novelty and emotional resonance. (p 18).

Later when Fiona saves Adam`s life, he still interrupts her life by writing letters, her memories and symbolic associations. He becomes a persistent psychological figure, while permanent stable world of law and court turns into background. Such situations directly show how moral decisions are able to rearrange the position of characters, turning the novel into field of cognitive salience in narrative ethics.

The theory of prototype, shown in the 3rd chapter, assumes that readers understand characters and situations by comparing them with "the best samples" of certain categories (Stockwell, Cognitive Poetics, p 27-33). People turn to familiar cognitive models in order to interpret new information in the text. These prototypes are formed culturally, socially and personally, that`s why the characters of Ian McEwan challenge our expectations and predictions.

Fiona, the figure of judge, carries very strong cultural prototype, she is very authoritative, rational, devoted, detached and emotionally neutral. At the beginning of the novel Fiona completely suits her prototype, she is very reserved, accurate, devoted to her juridical work. Her concrete sayings and order of procedure in the court strengthen her position in cognitive category. Later the author complicates Fiona`s prototype adding personal vulnerability to professional composure. The conflict with husband, where he reveals about his romance, loosens the prototype and reader sees the character from several cognitive frameworks simultaneously.

Adam Henry is also shown through several prototypes. As a 17-year-old Jehovah`s Witness, who refuses from blood transfusion, first he reminds the prototype of a devout teenage, who follows his family doctrine. This prototype vanishes immediately when he meets with Fiona. He demonstrates intellectual curiosity, artistic skills, emotionality rather what we expect to see weakness and humility. The description of the scene when he plays the violin makes him closer to the prototype of gifted, talented, romantic young man. The combination of several prototypes makes the character cognitively striking and memorable, strengthening his subsequent attachment to Fiona.

Stockwell mentioned in his book that a reader is more engaged when text includes several prototypes, leading a change in cognitive categorization. (p. 31) Ian McEwan effectively uses this technique to rise engagement and moral involvement of a reader. Fiona`s decision is not just a legal verdict, but a collision of mismatched prototypes: adult judge and dreaming teenage that force a reader to rethink what "adolescence", "autonomy" and "child interest" are. These mismatched prototypes create ethical complexity of the novel because none of the characters suits to expected cognitive category.

Cognitive Deixis, as mentioned by Stockwell, concerns the linguistic and conceptual cues that anchors the reader within a narrative world by indicating who is speaking, where the actions take place, how perspectives shift (Stockwell, *Cognitive Poetics*, p. 41-47). Deictic markers are spatial references, time frames that let a reader follow character movements and their mind thoughts flow. Ian McEwan uses deictic structuring in the novel *The Children Act* to deepen a reader into Fiona Maye's perception, creating intimacy, alignment and tension. Fiona functions as a primary deictic center. The narration organizes space around her: her room, flat, hospital and court. When she enters Adam's hospital room, the narration is built on her feelings and emotions, she notices its "clean emptiness," the soft beeping" of machinery, and Adam's thin, pale appearance as he speaks from the bed (pp. 118-119) These spatial cues create deictic shift from formal and controlled space of court to vulnerable space of hospital. A reader shares with Fiona her uncertainty in a new environment.

An important part in the novel is devoted to temporal deixis, when Fiona recalls her past events like marriage, past judgements, her own childlessness. These spontaneous time movements reflect non-linear narration of the novel and the deixis help readers follow the movement between "multiple nested worlds" (p 46) Comparing court cases and her personal memories creates a layered understanding of Fiona's decisions, showing how her past influences on her judicial present. The letters that Adam sends to Fiona form emotional and conceptual bridge. When pleading, fragile, disoriented Adams appears in front of Fiona, it forces her to renegotiate her emotional and spatial distance. Ian McEwan let a reader be not only an observer of judicial procedure, but a part of inner and outer world of Fiona with a help of deictic movements. As a result, a reader experiences how personal and professional boundaries can be blurred.

Cognitive poetics is a powerful tool that helps understand how *The Children Act* constructs, complicates and ruins ethical worlds of main characters. The analysis of the novel through figures and ground, prototypes, deixis, cognitive grammar, schemas, discourse worlds, conceptual metaphors, parabolic structure lets to see that the real problem (conflict) not in a legal dilemma. The author involves a reader into cognitive and emotional process, reflecting inner feelings and worries of Fiona Maye as a judge, a participant and a human being.

References:

1. *The Children Act*, Ian McEwan, First Anchor Books Edition, April 2015
2. *Cognitive Poetics in Practice*, Edited by Joanna Gavins and Gerard Steen, Routledge 2003
3. *Cognitive Poetics Introduction*, Peter Stockwell, Routledge 2002
4. <https://www.theguardian.com/books/2014/sep/11/the-children-act-ian-mcewan-review-novel>
5. <http://psasir.upm.edu.my/id/eprint/114267/1/114267.pdf>
6. https://brill.com/view/journals/mnya/23/1/article-p1_1.xml